

Preliminary results from the working group mental health of the German University Association UniWiND

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Purpose

The German university association UniWiND has defined its mission as optimising the circumstances and conditions for doctoral and postdoctoral researchers in order to support them in their academic work and future careers. As an organisation of over 80 member universities in Germany, it regularly publishes recommendations and guidelines on topics that are of general importance for early career researchers, such as supervision, skills training, quality assurance of PhD programs and so forth. The UniWiND working group on mental health consists of representatives from approximately 20 structured PhD programs throughout Germany and is due to publish its report with recommendations for supporting the wellbeing of early career researchers at the end of 2023 or the beginning of 2024.

Design

A combination of literature research, a nation-wide (Germany) questionnaire targeting management of structured PhD programs, interviews and best-practice examples.

Results (if applicable)

Initial results indicate that there is a significant mismatch in the perceived need for institutional support of early career researcher mental health and the actual provision of such support. In recent years, some institutions have started implementing programs directly targeting early career researcher mental health, and those that did report that this is extensively made use of and receives good feedback in general. More detailed analysis of the results of the questionnaire is in progress.

Implications

The recommendations of the UniWiND working group on mental health aims to provide actionable incentives for Universities to improve wellbeing support of early career researchers.

Acknowledgments

The UniWiND working group on mental health. This article is based upon work from the ReMO COST Action on Researcher Mental Health, CA19117, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

Resources

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